

Teaching Astronomy at Educational Level

A TASTE of research

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Although we can observe the Sun and stars moving in the sky easily, many people have difficulties to properly explain and even describe these apparent motions [e.g., 1-6]. Compared with other astronomical topics taught in schools, understanding apparent motions seems rather difficult. As the set-up that needs to be understood is truly three-dimensional, it cannot be reduced to two-dimensional diagrams. Moreover, stellar and solar motion have similarities, but also key differences. Understanding what is going on requires students to develop adequate mental models - and as also the research part of TASTE shows, several students have difficulties with this requirement.

Teaching these phenomena seems not easy. The design of teaching/learning activities that effectively support student learning in this context, therefore, requires special attention and detailed insight in student thinking.

In the TASTE project, we extended earlier research [7, 8] by carrying out two research studies. In a first study, we used the earlier developed AMoSS test (Apparent Motion of Sun and Stars) to study students' mental models in the participating countries; in a second study, we tested the effectiveness of a teaching/learning sequence that was developed in the context of the TASTE project. Special attention was paid to the possible role of a planetarium therein.

In what follows, we describe the main ideas and findings of both studies. The text is based on the research papers that are published in or submitted to the Astronomy Education Journal. For more background, detailed information on earlier research and the corresponding references and the applied methods, we refer to these research papers.

Study 1: Student ideas on the apparent motions of the Sun and the stars

Link to research paper in *Astronomy Education Journal*:

<https://astroedjournal.org/index.php/ijae/article/view/38/36>

Although astronomy is often considered as one of the sciences that can appeal to a wide audience and an entry point to science education, many astronomical concepts like the day/night cycle, the causes of the seasons or the Moon phases are difficult to grasp and teach. Similarly, the description and the explanation of the apparent motions of the Sun and the stars is hard for both students and adults to.

In the context of the TASTE project, we extended earlier research on students' mental models on the apparent motion of the Sun and the stars [7, 8] to a European context: we administered the AMoSS test [7] to students in the participating countries to study their insight in the apparent motion of the Sun and the stars.

The AMoSS test in the version used by TASTE consists of 12 multiple-choice questions aimed at testing basic understanding of the apparent motion of the Sun and the stars over the course of a day, a year, and for different observer locations on Earth. The test was deliberately kept short, to allow test administration, e.g., during a school lesson or planetarium visit. The possible answers to its multiple-choice questions were designed to probe common (incorrect) alternative conceptions students may have.

The twelve AMoSS questions cover the following topics:

I. Apparent motion of the Sun	II. Apparent motion of a star
I.A Daily sun position changes: Sun's path	II.A Nightly star position changes: star trail
I.B Sun culmination changes during a year	II.B Star culmination: no change during a year
I.C Sunrise/sunset positions change during a year	II.C Star-rise/-set positions: no change during a year
I.D Sun culmination depends on observer position	II.D Star culmination depends on observer position
I.E Sunrise/sunset position depend on location	II.E Star-rise/-set position depend on location
III. Seasons and Earth's orbital motion	IV. Sky map changes due to Earth's orbital motion

In the first phase of the project, we administered the test to a total of 348 students, 13 to 17 years old, in the four participating countries. The test (originally written in Dutch and translated to English) was translated in German, Greek and Italian. For each question, beyond the multiple-choice answer, we asked students "Explain your choice," with a blank box allowing them to write down their reasoning in words and/or in the form of little sketches.

To analyse student answers, we used a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods.

We scored the multiple-choice answers by awarding 1 point to a correct alternative, and 0 points to an incorrect or blanco answer. We also used a Latent Class Analysis (statistical method) to look for possible patterns in the students' answers.

To get more insight in student reasoning and give meaning to the patterns found by the Latent Class Analysis, we studied the written explanations in detail: a validated categorization scheme helped to systematically look at the student answers. It allowed to get deeper understanding of student reasoning: do they argue based on observations or the geocentric point of view or do they really use the allocentric model to explain the phenomena? Do they use the daily motion, the yearly motion, the properties of the Earth as a globe in their explanation? ...

Based on both the statistical and the qualitative analysis, the main findings are:

- overall, test scores are low;
- Sun questions are answered more correctly than star questions and student performance is similar across countries;
- based on the written answers and the Latent Class Analysis, we can identify several student ideas:
 1. STARS ACT LIKE THE SUN: A first group of students knows that the Sun and stars apparently move from east to west during the day and night. Students in this group answer star-related questions in such a way that the stars seem to behave exactly the same as the Sun. For both the Sun and the stars the path of the apparent motion is higher and wider in summer than it is in winter. When the observer's latitude decreases, this path becomes higher and wider both for the Sun and the stars.
 2. THE STARS ARE DIFFICULT TO GRASP: A second group of students knows that the apparent motion of the Sun and the stars is from east to west. They answer most Sun questions correctly, but for the star questions, an incorrect answer or 'I don't know' is selected.
 3. A third group of students also knows that the Sun and the stars appear to move from east to west, but they are characterized by the fact that they think that the Sun's path and star trails do not change throughout the year. They do not know how the observer's position relates to the Sun's path and the star trails.
 4. In this group, we distinguish between the time-related questions and the position-related questions. These students know that the Sun and the stars appear to move from east to west. They also know how the Sun's path changes throughout the year, but they are confused about the stars. If the observer changes position, they think that the Sun's path does not change, and they do not know how the star trail changes.
 5. These students answer only the question on the daily motion of the Sun and the seasons but indicate for all other questions 'I don't know'.

Although we could identify these groups of students adopting similar reasoning, we also realised that most students are not coherent in their answers on the different questions related to Sun and stars. Most students use factual arguments or observations in their explanations, but do not rely on elements of an allocentric view (the view from space) to reason about the Sun and stars.

Literature [9] shows that students that can think in a geocentric and allocentric frame of reference, are more likely to develop a better insight in basic astronomical phenomena. It seems to be crucial to support students to learn and think about the celestial motions in different frames of reference and to switch between the geocentric and allocentric perspective.

In the context of the TASTE project, several teaching/learning activities were developed to support student learning of the apparent motion of Sun and stars. The effectiveness of these activities was studied in the second phase of the project.

Study 2: Teaching the apparent motion of Sun and stars across four European countries

The research results on this study are submitted as a research paper to [Astronomy Education Journal](#) and will become available online when it is accepted.

Based on knowledge from literature (student difficulties in astronomy, possibilities of planetaria in supporting student learning, importance of perspective switching, etc.) and our own findings in the first phase of the TASTE-project, the project partners, with the teachers and planetarium staff, collaboratively designed teaching/learning activities to support student understanding of crucial elements like spatial scales and time related to the apparent motion of the Sun and stars. This resulted in a learning module where the concept of the celestial sphere is introduced, two planetarium workshops where students learn to use 2D- and 3D-models of Earth and the celestial sphere, and a planetarium presentation in the dome.

These teaching/learning activities were implemented by the different project partners in a research study to test to what extent they helped the students to gain insight in the apparent motion of celestial bodies.

In section 2.1, we describe the teaching/learning activities; in section 2.2, we describe the research to test the effectiveness and the main results.

2.1 Teaching/learning materials

To design the teaching/learning materials, we started from the main findings of the first phase of the project: most students performed better on the Sun-related questions than on the star-related questions and many students failed to use a proper scientific model to explain their answer. We therefore decided to teach the students about the celestial motions using the model of the celestial sphere. Since we believe that a planetarium can be an ideal tool to visualise the different aspects of this 3D model, we developed two planetarium workshops and a new planetarium presentation. To prepare

for the planetarium activities, we developed a teaching/learning module to implement at school before visiting the planetarium.

The development of the teaching/learning materials was a collaborative effort of teachers, researchers and planetarium staff that considered the following constraints:

- The activities should not assume any prior knowledge. They must be accessible to secondary school students of 13-18 years old.
- Because science teachers are constantly under time pressure, the learning module at school should be completed in two standard lessons of 40 minutes each.
- All activities should be hands-on, so that students actively engage with the concepts being taught.
- To schedule the various planetarium activities on one school day, the workshops and planetarium presentation should not exceed 4 hours.
- The planetarium presentation should be suitable for display in both analogue and digital planetariums.
- All activities should be presented in the students' native language.

The development of the activities was an iterative process. We implemented two test runs with pupils and teachers from the different participating countries during student mobilities and asked them to provide feedback. Based on this feedback, we adapted and fine-tuned the materials.

Learning module

The first part of the activities consists of a module that is aimed at preparing the planetarium visit. The module is meant for a teaching period of 80 minutes.

The main ideas of this module are:

- It consists of 2 parts: Part 1 focuses on the daily motion of the Sun and stars. Part 2 deals with the changes in the Sun's path and star trails throughout the year.
- Each part starts from observations (photographs, Stellarium). These observations put students in the geocentric perspective and ask for careful descriptions of what they observe.
- Each concept is introduced both for the Sun and for the stars. As such, we challenge students to focus on differences and similarities between solar and stellar phenomena.
- In the different exercises, students are challenged to switch perspectives and to connect the geocentric and the allocentric perspective.

To build a coherent and correct mental model, we introduce the model of the celestial sphere. All elements like celestial sphere, horizon plane of an observer, zenith, celestial equator, ecliptic, Pole star, culmination height, ... are carefully introduced and practiced with special attention to perspective taking.

Planetarium workshop 1: 3D model of the Earth and the celestial sphere

In this workshop, the students practice the concepts which they learned during the learning module at school. They use 3D models of the Earth and the celestial sphere and focus on an allocentric point of view. First, the concept of the parallel globe is introduced. This is a 3D model of the Earth, on which you can place different observers using magnets. The Earth's axis can be tilted so that the observer is at the very top of the globe. In the exercises, students discover that Polaris' altitude varies from one location to another and that it indicates the observer's latitude. In the second part, students use a celestial sphere, which is built with easy-to-find materials: a round flask (celestial sphere), a stick (Earth's axis), a ping-pong ball (Earth) and water (horizon). They indicate the celestial equator and the ecliptic on this so called "bottle globe" [10]. By changing the inclination of Earth's axis, students practice locating Polaris for different locations of the observer. In small exercises, students locate the Sun on the ecliptic for different times throughout the year and they discover that the Sun's path depends on this position on the ecliptic, while the star trails do not change throughout the year.

Figure 1: 3D model of Earth and "bottle globe" model

Planetarium presentation

The planetarium presentation deals with the apparent motion of the Sun and stars. It consists of three parts: the apparent daily motion of the Sun and stars, the apparent annual motion of the Sun and the role of the observer's location on the spherical Earth. Since not all planetariums have a digital projection system, the presentation only focuses on the geocentric point of view. After an element of the Sun's apparent motion is explained and shown, it is explained and shown also for the stars immediately afterwards, to highlight the similarities and differences between the Sun and the stars. To keep the students' attention, the presentation lasts maximum 1 hour and interactivity is stimulated by regularly asking questions to the audience.

Planetarium workshop 2: Planisphere

Figure 2: Planisphere

In the second planetarium workshop, students use of the planisphere, which is a 2D representation of the celestial sphere. Special about the TASTE planisphere, developed by the Planetario di Modena, is that it has two sides: one for the northern and one for the southern hemisphere. Each side consists of two rotating discs: a disc with the star map, and a disc with the observer's horizon, depending on the observer's latitude. By rotating the horizon disc, students visualize the daily motion of the stars from east to west. They learn that the times of star rise and star set change throughout the year. In the exercises they realize that - for a specific location on Earth - some stars never set, and other stars never rise. Students are stimulated to use their smartphone with the "Heavens above" app (developed by Chris Peat) installed and compare the visualisations of the planisphere with the images of the smartphone app.

2.2 Studying the effectiveness of the designed materials

To test the effectiveness of the designed teaching/learning activities, we used a two-treatment study with pretest post-test design: we compared two 'treatments' or implementations of the materials and tested student ideas both before (pre) and after (post) the implementation by administering the AMoSS test as a measurement instrument.

Two treatments

The German, Greek and Italian students who participated in this study followed the full sequence of activities in their native language, since a planetarium in their school's neighbourhood also participated in this study. Although the Brussels planetarium participated in the TASTE-project, it was not involved in the research part. Therefore, the planetarium workshops and the planetarium presentation could not be organized for the Belgian students. They followed only the learning module at school. We took this as an opportunity to setup a two-treatment study to test the extent to which the planetarium activities increase learning gains compared to students who do not visit a planetarium. To allow Belgian students to also engage with the 3D model of the celestial sphere physically, some exercises were added to the Belgian version of the learning module in which students used the 3D model at school, while the others used it at the planetarium. A model was chosen that could be used quickly and easily in an ordinary classroom. It was a restyled version of a commercially available tool (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: 3D model of celestial sphere, used by Belgian students

Main findings

The AMoSS test was administered as pretest and post-test in multiple-choice format only, due to time constraints in test taking. Student answers were again analysed by scoring a correct answer with 1 point and an incorrect or blanco one with 0 points. These answers were also used in a Latent Class Analysis to look for possible patterns in students' answers.

The main findings can be summarised as follows:

- Pretest results:
 - The pretest results of the German, Greek and Italian students are similar; the pretest results of the Belgian students are a bit better. This might be related to the age of the Belgian students that is a bit higher.
 - For all countries, the mean score of the Sun-related questions is systematically higher than for the star-related questions.
- Post-test results:
 - Belgian students perform better on the post-test than German, Greek and Italian students.
 - Learning gain from pretest to post-test is significant in all countries.
 - Students who only took the class activity made the same progress as students taking both the class and the planetarium activities.
- There are clear differences between treatment groups when we look at learning gains per question:
 - Daily motion of stars: German, Greek and Italian students' results improve significantly; Belgian students' results hardly improve. This might be related to the fact that Belgian students did not visit a (geocentric) planetarium where the apparent motion of stars was explicitly simulated.
 - Star trails throughout the year: Belgian students show clear learning gain; other groups show only small gains or even loss.
 - Seasons and change of star sky throughout the year: all students improve on the post-test, also for the stars.

The fact that students from two treatment groups show different learning gains on different questions indicates that finding the right approach can make a clear difference in the extent to which students increase their understanding of the apparent motion of the Sun and stars. Following a planetarium presentation in the dome helps to get a better view of the diurnal apparent motion of the stars during the night. Working with a 3D model of the celestial sphere during lessons at school, helps to learn how the Sun's path or the star trails may or may not depend on the time of the year. We suggest to use a 3D model of the celestial sphere to explain the apparent celestial motions both in the classroom and during the planetarium presentation in the dome. It will help the students to learn and switch between a geocentric and an allocentric point of view.

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